

Jnanadeepa

Pune Journal of Religious Studies

Dimensions of Priesthood

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<i>Jnanadeepa</i> Journal details	2
Editorial.....	3
Treasuring the Word. Biblical Hermeneutics in Priestly Ministry <i>Nishant A. Irudayadason</i>	4
Priest - Celebrant of the Cosmic Sacrament: Some Reflections on Holy Eucharist and Priestly Ministry <i>Isaac Parackal, OIC</i>	26
The Ecclesial Vocation of the Priest. A Vatican Council II Perspective <i>Errol D'Lima, S.J.</i>	42
The Challenges Priests Face in India Today <i>Kurien Kunnumpuram, S.J.</i>	65
“You are ... a royal priesthood ... so that you may announce ...” (1 Pet. 2:9). Reflections of two lay female theologians <i>Anna Findl-Ludescher and Teresa Peter</i>	91
The Priest and Communications <i>Jacob Srampickal, S.J.</i>	117
A Sad Chapter Of Church History <i>Julian Saldanha, S.J.</i>	142

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Editorial

The opening words of this editorial are words of gratitude to Fr. Kurien Kunnumpuram, S.J., who started this Journal as its first editor in January 1998. *Jnanadeepa* will be always grateful and indebted to you, Fr. Kurien, for these years of selfless, committed and dedicated service. You gave this Journal a vision, as you wrote in your very first editorial: “*Jnanadeepa* seeks to provide a critical, creative and interdisciplinary approach so that the major questions of our times can be studied from various perspectives.” You have upheld this vision. Thank you very, very much. Your blessings and support will help tremendously to keep progressing on the path that you have shown.

A word of gratitude to all who subscribe to this Journal, and to every person who reads it. Your support and good wishes are greatly appreciated. Suggestions are most welcome. Please do feel free to write to the editor.

Being the “Year of the Priest”, the basic theme of this issue is “Dimensions of the Priesthood”. Hope this year has helped all, not just priests alone, to study and reflect on priesthood in the Church. *Jnanadeepa* endeavours to do its part in this enterprise. The next issue, due in July 2010, will look at some more aspects of the priesthood.

Thomas Kuriacose, S.J.
Editor.